

YUQORI TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARNING TARTIBINI PASAYTIRISH

o'qituvchi E.A.Husanov, talaba F.A. Pardayeva
Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11235585

Annontatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yuqori tartibli differensial tenglamaning tartibini pasaytirishga doir nazariy va amaliy misollar o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Yuqori tartibli differensial tenglama.

Annotation. In this article, theoretical and practical examples of the reduction of the order of a high-order differential equation are studied.

Keywords. Higher order differential equation.

Аннотация. В данной статье изучены теоретические и практические примеры понижения порядка дифференциального уравнения высокого порядка.

Ключевые слова. Дифференциальное уравнение высшего порядка.

Ta'rif. Ushbu $F(x, y, y', \dots, y^{(n)}) = 0$ (1) ko'rinishdagi tenglama n-tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama deyiladi.

Bu yerda $F(x, y, y', \dots, y^{(n)})$ funksiya $(n+2)$ o'lchovli R^{n+2} fazoning D_{n+2} soxasida aniqlangan. Ko'p xollarda (1) tenglama ushbu

$$y^{(n)} = f(x, y, y', \dots, y^{(n-1)})$$

ko'rinishga keltiriladi. Bu tenglama yuqori tartibli xosilaga nisbatan yechilgan yoki kanonik ko'rinishdagi n-tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama deb yuritiladi. n-tartibli differensial tenglama nomalum funksiya y va uning ketma-ket kelgan xosilalari $y, y', \dots, y^{(k-1)}$ qatnashmasi deylik. U xolda differensial tenglama $F(x, y^{(k)}, y^{(k+1)}, \dots, y^{(n)})$, $(1 \leq k \leq n)$ ko'rinishda yoziladi.

Bu xolda $y^{(k)} = z$ deyilsa, $F(x, z, z', \dots, z^{(n-k)}) = 0$ $(n-k)$ - tartibi pasaygan differensial tenglama xosil bo'ladi. Agar n-tartibli differensial tenglamada erkli o'zgaruvchi oshkor xolda qatnashmasa yani tenglama $F(y, y', \dots, y^{(n)}) = 0$ ko'rinishda bo'lsa, uni yangi erkli o'zgaruvchi, $p = \frac{dy}{dx}$ ni yangi nomalum funksiya deb, ushbu almashtirishni bajaramiz.

$$y' = p.$$

$$y'' = \frac{dp}{dx} = \frac{dp}{dy} \cdot \frac{dy}{dx} = p \frac{dp}{dy},$$

$$y''' = \frac{dy''}{dx} = \frac{d}{dy} \left(p \frac{dp}{dy} \right) \frac{dy}{dx} = p \left[p \frac{d^2 p}{dy^2} + \left(\frac{dp}{dy} \right)^2 \right] = p^2 \frac{d^2 p}{dy^2} + p \left(\frac{dp}{dy} \right)^2, \dots$$

Bu hisoblashlar yordamida $\frac{d^k y}{dx^k}$ miqdor $p, \frac{dp}{dy}, \dots, \frac{d^{(k-1)} p}{dy^{(k-1)}}$ miqdorlar orqali ifodalanishi matematik induksiya usuli bilan ko'rsatish mumkin. Shu almashtirishni bajarsak $(k - 1) -$ tartibli $F_1(y, p, \frac{dp}{dy}, \dots, \frac{d^{(n-1)} p}{dy^{(n-1)}}) = 0$ differensial tenglamaga kelamiz.

Demak ko'rilayotgan xolda differensial tenglamaning tartibini bittaga kamaytirish mumkin.

1-Misol. Differensial tenglamani tartibini pasaytirish orqali yeching.

$$x^3 y'' + x^2 y' = 1$$

$$x^3 y'' + x^2 y' = 1$$

$$y' = p(x) = p$$

$$y'' = p'(x) = p'$$

$$x^3 p' + x^2 p = 1$$

$$p' + \frac{1}{x} p = \frac{1}{x^3}$$

$$p = u(x)v(x) = uv$$

$$p' = u'v + uv'$$

$$u'v + uv' + \frac{1}{x} uv = \frac{1}{x^3}$$

$$\left(u' + \frac{1}{x} u \right) v + \left(uv' - \frac{1}{x^3} \right) = 0$$

$$a) \quad u' + \frac{1}{x} u = 0$$

$$\frac{du}{dx} + \frac{u}{x} = 0$$

$$\int \frac{du}{u} = -\int \frac{dx}{x}$$

$$\ln |u| = -\ln |x| + \ln |C|$$

$$u = \frac{C}{x} \quad C^* = CC_1$$

$$y' = p = uv = -\frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{C^*}{x}$$

$$y = \frac{1}{x} + C^* \ln |x| + C_2$$

$$b) \quad uv' - \frac{1}{x^3} = 0$$

$$\frac{C dv}{x dx} - \frac{1}{x^3} = 0$$

$$\int dv = \int \frac{dx}{Cx^2}$$

$$v = -\frac{1}{Cx} + C_1$$

2-Misol. Differensial tenglamani tartibini pasaytirish orqali yeching.

$$yy'' = (y')^2 - (y')^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 yy'' &= (y')^2 - (y')^3 \\
 y' &= p(y) = p \\
 y'' &= p'(y)y' = p'p \\
 yp'p &= p^2 - p^3 \\
 p &= 0, \quad y_1 = C_1 \\
 p' - \frac{p}{y} + \frac{p^2}{y} &= 0 \\
 p &= u(y)v(y) = uv \\
 p' &= u'v + uv' \\
 u'v + uv' - \frac{uv}{y} + \frac{u^2v^2}{y} &= 0 \\
 \left(u' - \frac{u}{y}\right)v + \left(v' + \frac{uv^2}{y}\right)u &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$a) \quad u' - \frac{u}{y} = 0$$

$$\frac{du}{u} = \frac{dy}{y}$$

$$\int \frac{du}{u} = \int \frac{dy}{y}$$

$$\ln |u| = \ln |y| + \ln |C|$$

$$u = Cy$$

$$y' = p = uv = 1$$

$$y_2 = x + C_2$$

$$b) \quad v' + \frac{uv^2}{y} = 0$$

$$\frac{dv}{v^2} + C dy = 0$$

$$\int \frac{dv}{v^2} = -\int C dy$$

$$v = \frac{1}{Cy}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Sh.R.Xurramov. Oliy matematika (masalalar to'plami, nazorat to'plami, topshiriqlar to'plami). 2015 y.

2. Краснов М. Л., Киселев А. И., Макаренко Г. И. Сборник задач по обыкновенным дифференциальным уравнениям. — 3-е изд. — М.: Высшая школа, 1978.

3. Самойленко А. М., Кривошея С. А., Перестюк Н. А. Дифференциальные уравнения: примеры и задачи. — 2-е изд. — М.: Высшая школа, 1989.